

Reconfigurable Magnetic Soft Microrobot for Acoustically Triggered Targeted Bacterial Sterilization

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Several nanomaterials have been proposed for antibacterial applications, offering promising strategies to combat infections as antibiotic resistance continues to rise due to widespread misuse. However, their clinical translation remains limited by poor localization and the lack of active control at the target site. Here, a thermoresponsive, shape-reconfigurable hydrogel-based magnetic microrobot is presented that addresses these challenges by integrating piezoelectric zinc oxide (ZnO) nanorods directly onto its soft, dynamic surface. The nanorods are densely grown in situ, enabling localized, acoustically triggered bacterial sterilization. The reconfigurability of the microrobot provides functional versatility: in its swollen, helical state, embedded magnetic nanoparticles allow effective magnetic maneuvering in fluidic environments. When heated above the swelling–deswelling transition temperature, the robot flattens to increase surface contact, enhancing interaction with biological targets. Under ultrasound stimulation, the ZnO nanorods undergo mechanical bending, triggering piezocatalysis and generating reactive oxygen species near the target site. This multifunctional platform combines active navigation, dynamic shape change, and localized antibacterial action, offering a new strategy for integrating functional nanomaterials into soft, reconfigurable devices with future therapeutic potential.

(AMR),^[2,3] a critical global health threat responsible for millions of fatalities.^[4] The growing threat of AMR has accelerated the search for strategies to manage difficult-to-treat bacterial infections, with two main approaches emerging. One focuses on improving how antibiotics are used, ensuring they are prescribed more carefully and only when truly needed. The other aims to develop alternative therapies that can fight infections without relying on conventional antibiotics.

Several approaches have been explored to achieve bacterial sterilization while minimizing the risk of promoting AMR.^[5] These include antimicrobial peptides,^[6,7] nanomaterials-based disinfection platforms,^[8–10] phage therapy,^[11,12] targeted drug delivery,^[13,14] and combinatorial treatments.^[15] Among them, several nanomaterials show promise as they can mimic immune responses by generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) via mechanisms such as biocatalysis,^[16–20] piezocatalysis,^[21] or photodynamic activation.^[22,23] Biocatalysis relies on local

chemical reactants, which may be scarce in hypoxic infection sites, while photodynamic therapy is limited by the low penetration of light, typically ≈ 1 mm for visible wavelengths and 10 mm for near-infrared.^[24–26] In contrast, piezoelectric materials can be remotely instructed to produce ROS in aqueous environments by means of ultrasound without relying on local reactants.^[27] Among available piezocatalysts, ZnO stands out as

1. Introduction

Bacterial infections elicit complex immune responses and, in severe cases, can significantly compromise health.^[1] Broad-spectrum antibiotics have been widely used to combat bacterial transmission and colonization. Yet, their overuse and mismanagement have accelerated the rise of antimicrobial resistance

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the ideal candidate as it is FDA-approved and displays a high piezoelectric performance.^[28] Nevertheless, challenges remain in the systemic delivery of ZnO nanorods and in maintaining the efficacy of the generated ROS, as these are highly reactive and display short lifetimes and limited diffusion in aqueous or biofilm environments.^[29] In complex biological fluids, various scavengers can rapidly quench these species, further restricting their effective range.^[30] Together, these factors highlight the need for localized ROS generation and prolonged activity to achieve effective sterilization.

To overcome these challenges, researchers have proposed using micro- and nanomotors for the targeted delivery of antibacterial agents. Propelled by catalytic reactions or external energy inputs, these devices can deliver anti-bacterial cargo such as antibiotics,^[31–33] anti-infective agents,^[34–36] or anti-biofilm treatments^[18,37–40] directly to infected tissues. Targeted approaches can reduce therapeutic dosage while maintaining efficacy. Among various types of micro- and nanomotors, magnetically actuated small-scale robots are arguably the most promising,^[41] as magnetic fields enable their precise remote navigation and retention at infection sites. This enhanced maneuverability can support sustained, localized treatment, improving bacterial sterilization while reducing off-target effects.^[37–39,41] Microrobots can leverage complementary chemical and mechanical antibacterial mechanisms to achieve synergistic bacterial clearance.^[41,42] For example, ROS generation or drug release provides chemical activity, while magnetically induced motion exerts mechanical forces that damage bacterial membranes and disrupt biofilm structures. Additionally, by incorporating advanced features such as shape-morphing and tailored material design, microrobots can adapt to complex physiological environments, for example, by conforming to irregular surfaces to maximize contact area and local dosage.^[37] Microrobots can also act as physical barriers that restrict bacterial motility within confined spaces.^[43] Overall, these strategies suggest that combining magnetic targeting with controlled surface interaction and shape adaptability can enable effective localized antibacterial therapy.

In this paper, we introduce a magnetically controlled, shape-morphing soft microrobot for localized antibacterial therapy, as conceptually illustrated in **Figure 1**. The device features a multilayered structure composed of an active N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM)-based magnetic composite hydrogel and passive SU-8 structural layers (**Figure 1a**), forming a stable and biocompatible

platform for nanorod integration (**Figure 1b**). A common strategy embeds ZnO nanomaterials in a polymer matrix, but this often isolates them from the medium, limiting mechanical stimulation and catalytic activity. To address this, we developed a method for the in situ-growth of a dense, freestanding ZnO nanorod array directly on the microrobot surface. This configuration ensures full exposure to biological fluids and allows the nanorods to undergo significant mechanical deformation under ultrasound, enhancing ROS production at the interface.^[44] The microrobot responds to environmental temperature by reversibly transforming its shape, shifting from a helical form at lower temperatures to a flattened configuration when the temperature rises above the hydrogel's phase transition (≈ 36 °C). The planar configuration enables higher surface contact with the infected area. At the infection site, ultrasound stimulation is applied and induces mechanical bending of the ZnO nanorods (**Figure 1c**), triggering piezoelectric charge separation and localized electric fields.^[45–47] These fields drive redox reactions that generate ROS, including superoxide anions ($O_2^{\bullet-}$), hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet OH$), and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2).^[48] The flattened geometry helps retain ROS at the infection site (**Figure 1e**), enhancing sterilization while minimizing off-target effects. We systematically characterize the microrobot's shape-morphing behavior, magnetic navigation, and ultrasound-triggered antibacterial activity. This work establishes a multifunctional soft microrobot platform that integrates targeted navigation, adaptive geometry, and piezocatalytic therapy, offering a promising solution for delivery to infection sites that are difficult to treat systemically, such as in poorly vascularized regions (e.g., otitis externa or media^[49–52]) (**Figure 1d,e**).

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Fabrication of the ZnO Nanorod Integrated Magnetic Soft Microrobot

We fabricated a multilayer magnetic soft microrobot composed of a shape-morphing bilayer structure and a functional ZnO nanorod layer, as illustrated in **Figure 2a**. The bilayer consists of a thermoresponsive NIPAM-based hydrogel and a passive SU-8 layer, enabling reversible transformation from a helical to a planar configuration in response to temperature changes. The ZnO nanorods are grown in situ directly on the hydrogel surface rather than embedded within the matrix. The overall fabrication process comprises two main steps: 1) fabrication of the shape-morphing magnetic bilayer structure, and 2) surface functionalization via in situ growth of ZnO nanorods.

2.1.1. Shape Morphing Magnetic Microrobots Fabrication

The shape-morphable magnetic microrobot chassis serves as a structural carrier for ZnO nanorods, enabling targeted delivery to infected sites. We employed photolithography and molding lithography to realize the entire fabrication process of the microrobot chassis. The microrobot architecture comprises three major components: an isotropic passive constraint layer, an anisotropic passive constraint layer, and an active morphing layer. The active layer is composed of NIPAM hydrogel, which exhibits reversible swelling and dehydration at low and elevated

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Figure 1. Magnetically actuated shape-morphing soft microrobot for localized antibacterial therapy. a) Reversible transformation between planar and helical configurations in response to environmental temperature. b) Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanorods grown in situ on the hydrogel surface and embedded iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs) perpendicularly aligned for magnetic actuation. c) Ultrasound-mediated piezoelectric ROS generation for bacterial sterilization. d) Navigation of the helical microrobot toward the infected area via corkscrew motion under a rotating magnetic field. e) Temperature-triggered flattening enhances contact for localized treatment.

temperatures, respectively. We selected SU-8 for the passive layer materials due to its high Young's modulus, which provides both mechanical support and geometric constraint. The mismatch in swelling ratio between the NIPAM-based hydrogel and the SU-8 passive layer generates internal stress, which is converted into bending moments upon temperature change. The passive layer constrains this deformation, directing it into a controlled, self-twisting motion that stabilizes the microrobot in a helical configuration. To enable magnetic actuation, iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs) were embedded and directionally aligned within the hydrogel matrix during the molding lithography process.

As illustrated in Figure 2b, the whole fabrication process began with the formation of two passive SU-8 layers on a pre-patterned glass mask coated with a poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) sacrificial layer. First, an isotropic layer was spin-coated and patterned to support the structure during shape morphing and translate swelling-induced expansion into bending. To prevent the stress concentration in this layer, corners were rounded in the design (Figure S1a, Supporting Information). Next, an anisotropic scaffold layer was fabricated in the same way on top of the isotropic layer. The scaffold pattern was aligned at a 45° angle with respect to the microrobot's longitudinal axis (Figure S1b, Supporting Information), resulting in a non-diagonal bending stiffness matrix. This anisotropy induces out-of-plane twisting when a bending moment is applied, achieving the desired helical shape during swelling. In contrast to the passive layers fabricated by conventional photolithog-

raphy, the active hydrogel layer was fabricated using molding lithography.

Following passive layer fabrication, the glass mask bearing the patterned SU-8 structures was inverted and used as the molding lithography mask. A new silicon wafer, coated with a polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) sacrificial layer, served as the molding substrate. A spacer was employed to define the hydrogel layer thickness, which was pre-aligned during passive layer fabrication at designated regions. The chamber formed between the two wafers was filled with a hydrogel precursor solution containing dispersed IONPs. The assembled stack was then placed in a UV chamber within a Helmholtz coil setup, which applied a magnetic field to align the IONPs perpendicular to the scaffold orientation. While maintaining the magnetic field, UV light was applied through the transparent areas of the glass mask to cure the hydrogel and fix the nanoparticles in the desired orientation. After polymerization, the structure was immersed in water to dissolve the PVA layer, releasing the silicon wafer. The cured microrobot structure remained adhered to the glass mask, allowing for subsequent in situ growth of ZnO nanorods.

2.1.2. ZnO Piezoelectric Nanorods In Situ Growth

To enable in situ growth of the ZnO nanorods on the hydrogel surface of the microrobot chassis, both the seed and growth solutions were prepared as described in the Experimental Section (see also Figure S2, Supporting Information). As depicted

Figure 2. Fabrication and in situ growth process for constructing ZnO nanorod-functionalized magnetic soft microrobots. a) Schematic of the micro-robot's multilayer architecture, consisting of a ZnO nanorod layer, an active hydrogel layer with embedded IONPs, and two passive SU-8 constraint layers. b) Step-by-step fabrication of the microrobot chassis via photolithography and molding lithography. c) In situ hydrothermal growth process of the ZnO nanorod layer. d) Optical image of the microrobots adhered to the glass mask after ZnO nanorod growth. e) Microscopic image of a single helical microrobot. f) Photograph of a batch of ZnO-functionalized microrobots collected in a Petri dish.

in Figure 2c, the glass mask containing the microrobot chassis was then immersed in the seed solution for 10 min with the substrate facing downward. After immersion, the mask was placed on an empty container and transferred to a 90 °C oven for 5 min to anneal the ZnO seed crystals on the hydrogel surface. This immersion-annealing cycle was repeated three times to improve the uniformity and reliability of seed annealing. Subsequently, the glass mask with annealed seeds was transferred into the prepared ZnO growth solution. To avoid unwanted particle deposition from the bulk solution onto the structure surface, the glass wafer was inserted into the slit of a customized acrylic holder with an internal width slightly larger than the mask thickness. The robot side was tilted slightly downward to minimize particle sedimentation and promote clean surface growth. Then the entire setup was transferred into a 90 °C oven for 4 h to initiate in situ ZnO nanorod growth at the pre-

seeded sites, ensuring stable nanorod anchoring on the hydrogel surface.

As shown in Figure 2d, the microrobots remained adhered to the glass mask after the ZnO growth, which were subsequently released by immersion in propylene glycol methyl ether acetate (PGMEA) solvent. Next, the functionalized microrobots were collected for further testing. Hundreds of robots can be successfully fabricated in a single batch, demonstrating the scalability and mass production potential of this fabrication protocol. Importantly, the microrobots retained their shape-morphing ability after the ZnO growth process and successfully transformed into helical configurations, confirming that the hydrogel properties remain intact. This indicates that the relatively low annealing and growing temperatures (90 °C) are compatible with the thermoresponsive hydrogel. In Figure 2e, the hydrogel scaffolds are aligned along the axial direction, providing non-orthogonal

mechanical resistance and facilitating the structure to deform into a helical rather than a tubular shape. Additionally, the magnetic particles embedded in the hydrogel matrix were predominantly aligned along the radial direction, perpendicular to the robot's longitudinal axis. This alignment enables corkscrew motion propulsion under a rotating magnetic field, allowing net directional movement in a fluid medium and achieving precise navigation towards target sites. A batch of the fabricated ZnO-functionalized microrobots is shown in Figure 2f.

2.2. Characterization of the ZnO Nanorod-Functionalized Microrobots

Following successful fabrication, comprehensive characterization was performed to evaluate the structural integration, shape-morphing behavior, and locomotion performance of the ZnO nanorod-functionalized microrobots.

2.2.1. ZnO In Situ Growth Evaluation

To verify the successful in situ integration of ZnO nanorods onto the hydrogel surface of the microrobots, we performed scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging. As shown in Figure 3a, the microrobot hydrogel side was placed upward. The SEM images clearly revealed a dense and uniform layer of spatially grown ZnO nanorods, which is a critical factor influencing ROS generation. Both enlarged view and side-view images further confirmed the high uniformity and density of the nanorods. The enlarged top-view SEM image revealed the characteristic hexagonal cross-section typical of the wurtzite crystal structure of ZnO, providing morphological evidence of the crystal phase. The side view further confirmed that the nanorods were spatially grown rather than superficially deposited. From the images, the individual nanorod exhibited a diameter of ≈ 100 nm and a length of ≈ 1 μm . Notably, after more than six months of storage, the in situ-grown ZnO nanorods remained densely and uniformly distributed and firmly anchored to the microrobot surface (Figure S3, Supporting Information), demonstrating long-term integration stability. To further confirm the composition and elemental distribution, high-angle annular dark field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) coupled with energy dispersive x-ray dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) was performed. Figure 3b shows a single nanorod from the robot and the corresponding elemental mappings, with clear and co-localized signals for both Zn and O, confirming its composition as ZnO. The EDS spectrum (Figure 3c) displayed prominent peaks for Zn ($K\alpha$ at ≈ 8.6 keV and $K\beta$ at ≈ 9.6 keV) and O ($K\alpha$ at ≈ 0.52 keV), with no detectable impurity peaks, further validating the high material purity.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis (Figure 3d) shows that all observed peaks matched well with the standard diffraction pattern of ZnO (JCPDS 37-1451), confirming both high phase purity and crystallinity. Notably, the intensity of the [002] diffraction peak was significantly higher than that in the standard reference, indicating a preferential growth along the c -axis. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) imaging (Figure 3e, also see Figure S4, Supporting Information) further validated the hexagonal cross-

section morphology and structural consistency with the SEM results. High-resolution TEM (HRTEM) revealed that atomic lattice fringes were oriented along the [002] crystallographic direction. The interplanar spacings measured in two directions were ≈ 0.260 and ≈ 0.162 nm, consistent with the lattice constants of wurtzite ZnO.^[53,54] This preferential orientation during synthesis is critical for enhancing the piezoelectric properties of the nanorods in practical applications.

In addition, the selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern (Figure 3f) displays a series of sharp and well-defined diffraction spots, indicating the single-crystalline nature of ZnO nanorods. The prominent [002] reflection confirmed that the electron beam was aligned parallel to the c -axis of the nanorod, consistent with the preferential growth orientation from previous results. Additional diffraction spots corresponding to the [110] and [112] planes were symmetrically distributed around the central zone axis, further verifying the single-crystalline feature of the ZnO nanorods along their intrinsic anisotropic growth axis.

2.2.2. Evaluation of Magnetic Microrobot Shape Morphing and Localization

As designed, the hydrogel layer enabled temperature-triggered swelling and dehydration, allowing for reversible shape morphing. Given that hydrogels are relatively fragile and sensitive to extreme conditions, we first evaluated their structural integrity and morphing behaviors under varying temperatures in aqueous environments. As shown in Figure 3g (also see Video S1, Supporting Information), the microrobot immersed in cold water (20 °C) adopted a helical shape due to hydrogel swelling. The SU-8 scaffolds provided strong mechanical resistance, facilitating the deformation into a stable helical configuration. Notably, the embedded MNPs remained well-aligned, enhancing the robots' magnetic responsiveness and enabling stronger torque and improved directional locomotion control. At ≈ 40 °C, the robot gradually flattened within ≈ 100 s, demonstrating excellent reversible morphing and retention of hydrogel functionality. To assess whether morphing-induced stresses compromise attachment, we inspected the ZnO nanorods by SEM (Figure S5, Supporting Information). The nanorods remained intact and firmly anchored to the hydrogel with no signs of detachment or delamination. Taken together, with a transition temperature ≈ 36 °C and rapid, reversible shape transformation, the design is well-suited for semi-confined spaces such as biological cavities (e.g., the ear canal or nasal cavity), where short-range navigation is required. Because hydrogel-based components may lose responsiveness over time, we conducted a long-term stability assessment of the microrobot's morphing behavior. After storage for more than six months, the device still underwent the temperature-triggered transition to a flattened configuration and returned to its original shape, and this response remained reversible and repeatable over several consecutive cycles without evident loss of function (Figure S6, Supporting Information).

To assess the microrobot's locomotion capabilities, we conducted navigation tests within a three-axis rotating magnetic field generated by a 3-pair Helmholtz coil system (see Figure S7, Supporting Information). Under magnetic actuation, the microrobot exhibited corkscrew-like propulsion, as shown in Figure 3h (also

Figure 3. Structural and functional characterization of ZnO nanorod-functionalized microrobots. a) SEM images of ZnO nanorods grown on the hydrogel surface: (1) top-view, (2) enlarged top-view, and (3) side-view. b) HAADF-STEM image and corresponding EDS elemental mappings of a single ZnO nanorod. c) EDS spectrum of ZnO nanorods. d) XRD pattern matching the wurtzite ZnO standard (JCPDS 37–1451), indicating the crystallinity and preferential orientation. e) TEM and HRTEM images revealing well-defined lattice fringes aligned along the [002] direction. f) SAED pattern showing sharp diffraction spots confirming the single-crystalline ZnO and the dominant [002] orientation. g) Temperature-dependent shape morphing capabilities of the microrobots. h) Time-lapse images showing corkscrew propulsion under a rotating magnetic field (20 mT, 3 Hz). i) Rolling motion near a boundary under a rotating magnetic field (20 mT, 2 Hz), demonstrating adaptive locomotion behavior.

see Video S2, Supporting Information), confirming that locomotion performance was preserved after ZnO growth. The propulsion speed increased proportionally with rotation frequency (within a feasible range of field frequency) (see Figure S8, Supporting Information). In addition to corkscrew propulsion, the microrobots demonstrated adaptable locomotion behavior. When interacting with boundaries, they performed rolling movements to reach target locations (Figure 3h, also see Video S3, Supporting Information), broadening their use in constrained or irregular environments.

To further demonstrate the robot's functional capabilities, we conducted sequential navigation and shape-morphing experiments inside a channel under magnetic control (Video S4, Supporting Information). Under a rotating magnetic field, the micro-robot efficiently navigated to the target site via corkscrew propulsion, achieving speeds of $\approx 1.27 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ in a 20 mT rotating magnetic field and 0.68 mm s^{-1} in a gradient magnetic field exceeding 150 mT m^{-1} , within a liquid cell culture medium containing 10% fetal bovine serum. Under a rotating magnetic field, the micro-robot efficiently navigated toward the target site via corkscrew-like propulsion. This mode of actuation provided more controllable navigation than the magnetic field gradient. Upon reaching the target region, the robot underwent thermally induced flattening at an elevated temperature ($\approx 40^\circ\text{C}$), resulting in an increased exposure area, which could enhance the treatment efficacy considering the short lifetime of ROS.^[29,55]

2.3. Bacterial Sterilization Evaluation of the Magnetic Piezoelectric Microrobot

ROS, including hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$), superoxide anions ($\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$), and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), are known to damage bacterial cells by attacking membranes and essential biomolecules, ultimately leading to cell death.^[56] Leveraging the piezoelectric properties of ZnO, especially under mechanical deformation induced by ultrasonication, microrobots functionalized with ZnO nanorods can generate ROS and exhibit strong antibacterial effects. To assess their bacterial sterilization efficacy, we performed a colony-counting assay using *E. coli* ATCC 25 922, a reference Gram-negative strain for antibiotic susceptibility testing. Prior to antibacterial evaluation, biocompatibility was confirmed through HUVEC cell culturing experiments (Figure S9, Supporting Information), which demonstrated acceptable cytocompatibility, making it suitable for use.

Fabricated microrobots were mixed with a defined concentration of *E. coli* (details in Experimental Sections), followed by a 90 min ultrasonic stimulation. Multiple experimental groups were tested: with and without ultrasonication, microrobots with and without ZnO nanorods, ZnO nanoparticles as a positive control, and a bacterial-only group as a negative control. As shown in Figure 4a,b, in the absence of ultrasound, bacterial viability remained high across all groups except those treated with free ZnO nanoparticles. The reduction observed in the nanoparticle-treated group is attributed to membrane association and subsequent Zn^{2+} ion release, which can damage bacterial membranes.^[57] Notably, microrobots with and without ZnO showed no significant antibacterial effect in the absence of ultrasound, indicating that the microrobots alone do not inher-

ently release ROS or ions in static conditions, underscoring their biocompatibility. Upon ultrasound activation, both microrobots with ZnO nanorods and ZnO nanoparticles alone achieved over 90% bacterial sterilization. In contrast, microrobots without ZnO induced only a minor reduction (10.7%) in bacterial colonies. These findings also confirm that the ultrasound alone contributes partially to bacterial sterilization, consistent with previous studies.^[58]

To evaluate the kinetics of the bacterial sterilization, samples were collected at various intervals during an ultrasonication period of 90 min. As shown in Figure 4c, microrobots without the ZnO showed a negligible bactericidal effect across the entire 90-min period. In contrast, ZnO nanorod-functionalized microrobots triggered a rapid and pronounced decline in viable bacteria, with the majority of bacterial sterilization progress occurring within the first 20 min, as shown in Figure 4d. By 40 min, the bacterial count had dropped to near-maximal sterilization levels (97.3%), indicating that the antibacterial effect is both rapid and efficient. To determine whether ultrasound actuation compromises the attachment of the in situ-grown ZnO nanorods, we examined the microrobot surface by SEM after the ultrasound exposure (Figure S10, Supporting Information). The nanorod array remained dense and uniform, and the rods were still firmly anchored to the hydrogel chassis, with no detectable loss of coverage.

The pronounced performance difference between ZnO nanorod-functionalized microrobots and their blank counterparts underscores the crucial role of ZnO in mediating ROS generation. While mechanical stress from ultrasound may disrupt bacterial membranes to some extent, the additional electrochemical interactions induced by ZnO under ultrasound significantly enhance the efficacy of bacterial sterilization. Zn^{2+} ion release may also contribute to this effect by disrupting bacterial metabolism and membrane integrity. However, control experiments demonstrate that ion release alone is insufficient to achieve comparable antibacterial efficiency without ultrasonic treatment. Importantly, ZnO-functionalized microrobots remain largely inactive in the absence of ultrasound, indicating low cytotoxicity and enabling stimulus-responsive, localized therapy. This controllability enables site-specific bacterial sterilization while minimizing collateral damage to surrounding healthy tissues. In biological media containing radical scavengers, primary radicals are quickly quenched, limiting their lifetime and diffusion range. Magnetic targeting combined with thermally induced planar reconfiguration improves surface retention and contact, enabling ultrasound-driven piezocatalysis to generate a concentrated near-surface ROS flux before scavenging occurs. Meanwhile, longer-lived H_2O_2 species extend the antibacterial effect over tens to hundreds of micrometers, complementing the near-surface ROS action for synergistic sterilization in complex media.

2.4. Reactive Oxygen Species Generation of ZnO Piezoelectric Materials

To investigate the generation and identification of ROS induced by the piezoelectric effect, electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy was employed for ROS detection in the

Figure 4. Antibacterial evaluation of ZnO nanorod-functionalized microrobots under acoustic activation. a) Representative colony images of *E. coli* ATCC 25 922 after 90 min incubation under different treatments: bacteria only (control), free ZnO nanoparticles (positive), microrobots without ZnO, and ZnO-functionalized microrobots, with and without ultrasound. b) Quantitative colony-counting results corresponding to (a), confirming that ZnO nanorod-functionalized microrobots achieve >90% bacterial killing only under ultrasound stimulation ($n = 3$, data shown as mean \pm SD). c) Time-course colony images showing the sterilization kinetics of the functional microrobots during a 90-min ultrasonic treatment. d) Bacterial viability as a function of ultrasonication duration, showing more than 97% reduction within 40 min ($n = 3$; data represent mean \pm SD).

aqueous phase.^[59] Given the extremely short half-lives of most ROS species (typically $< 10^{-6}$ s),^[60] 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline N-oxide (DMPO) was utilized as a spin-trapping agent to capture transient radicals such as superoxide ($O_2^{\bullet-}$) and hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet OH$), as illustrated in Figure 5a. Under acoustic excitation, ZnO generates ROS via the redox reactions driven by the piezoelectric effect. And the generated ROS are effectively trapped by DMPO, forming stable adducts DMPO-OOH for superoxide radicals and DMPO-OH for hydroxyl radicals. These adducts exhibit distinct EPR signatures, enabling unambiguous identification of each ROS agent. As shown in Figure 5b, the DMPO-OOH adduct displayed six characteristic peaks with an intensity ratio of 1:2:2:1:2:2 after ultrasonication, confirming the generation of superoxide radicals. Similarly, the DMPO-OH adduct exhibited a typical four-peak pattern with an intensity ratio of 1:2:2:1 (Figure 5c), indicative of hydroxyl radical generation. Notably, no detectable signal was observed in the control group (0 min), indicating that ROS production is directly triggered by acoustic stimulation. Furthermore, a clear time-dependent increase in signal intensity was observed when the acoustic treatment duration increased from 0 to 5 and 10 min, indicating cumulative ROS generation. This trend correlates closely with the enhanced bactericidal efficacy observed in antimicrobial experiments and the results from photoluminescence spectroscopy (Figure S11, Supporting Information), confirming that the duration of ultrasonication is a critical parameter influencing ZnO-mediated ROS production and, consequently, sustained bacterial sterilization.

While individual ZnO particles and nanorods are known to generate ROS via piezoelectric-driven redox activity under acoustic excitation, the collective behavior of densely packed nanorods on the hydrogel surface remains less well understood. To address this, we performed finite element simulations using COMSOL Multiphysics to model and evaluate the electric potential distribution in ZnO nanorods embedded in the microrobot under various pressure magnitudes and loading directions, simulating dynamic mechanical-fluidic conditions during ultrasonication. As shown in Figure 5d, the simulated electric potential distribution varied with both the magnitude of the applied pressure (10, 50, and 100 MPa) and the loading direction (left, right, and top). Increasing pressure resulted in greater mechanical deformation of the nanorods, producing higher piezoelectric potentials, which is also consistent with other loading conditions (Figure S12, Supporting Information). Notably, lateral loading generated significantly larger potential differences compared to vertical (top-down) loading, due to the enhanced bending deformation of the nanorods, an effect absent in spherical nanoparticles, which primarily undergo compressive stress. These findings highlight the mechanical-electrical coupling advantages of high-aspect-ratio ZnO nanorods and support their ability to generate ROS via localized redox reactions under acoustic stimulation.

3. Conclusion

In summary, we have presented a shape-morphing magnetic soft microrobot functionalized with in situ-grown piezoelectric ZnO nanorods for ultrasound-triggered, localized bacterial sterilization. The thermoresponsive NIPAM-based hydrogel enables reversible transformation between helical and planar configurations, allowing both efficient navigation and enhanced surface

contact with infected tissue. To preserve hydrogel integrity while ensuring catalytic performance, we developed a low-temperature in situ ZnO nanorod growth strategy that enables dense, spatially controlled surface functionalization. This configuration significantly improves ROS generation under acoustic stimulation. Comprehensive characterization and in vitro assays confirm successful microrobot fabrication, controlled magnetic locomotion, and strong antibacterial efficacy, achieving over 95% bacterial reduction through ultrasound-induced ROS. This system offers a promising, antibiotic-free alternative for treating localized infections, particularly in poorly vascularized regions, while addressing key challenges related to targeting, retention, and AMR.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: N-Isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM, 97%), n-butanol (99.9%), bis-acrylamide (BIS, 99%), 1-methoxy-2-propanol acetate (99.5%), poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA, 80%), zinc acetate dihydrate (98%), 2-propanol (99%), triethylamine (99%), zinc nitrate hexahydrate (98%), hexamethylenetetramine (HTMA, 99%), (1-methoxy-2-propyl) acetate (99.5%), 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline-N-oxide (DMPO, 98%), acrylic acid (AAc, 99%), Luria Bertani broth (L3022), and Luria Bertani agar (L2897) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Photoinitiator Omnirad 2022 was supplied by S. u. K. Hock GmbH (Germany). SU-8 and PMMA photoresists were purchased from Kayaku Advanced Materials, and polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) coated IONPs were purchased from US Research Nanomaterials Inc. (USA).

Preparation of NIPAM-Based Magnetic Hydrogel Resin: The NIPAM-based magnetic hydrogel precursor was formulated by mixing NIPAM, BIS, n-butanol, and AAc in a molar ratio of 118:5:365:12. Omnirad 2022 (1 wt.%) was added as the photoinitiator. The mixture was magnetically stirred overnight for complete homogenization. Prior to use, IONPs (7 wt.%) were incorporated into the resin system.

Fabrication of Multilayer Microrobot Chassis: A chrome pattern was first defined on a 4-inch glass wafer, serving as both a fabrication substrate and a photomask for subsequent molding lithography. A 2 μm PMMA sacrificial layer was spin-coated and baked, followed by SU-8 spin-coating and patterning to create the 10 μm -thick isotropic layer. A second 10 μm -thick anisotropic SU-8 layer with a 45° aligned scaffold design was added to enhance anisotropic bending stiffness. Additionally, a 30 μm -thick SU-8 spacer was patterned to define the hydrogel thickness. All photolithography processes were completed using an MA/BA6 Gen4 mask aligner (SUSS MicroTec).

For the fabrication of the active layer using molding lithography, the SU-8 surface was functionalized through silanization and silicon-based coating to improve adhesion. At the same time, PVA was spin-coated and baked on a separate silicon wafer as the second sacrificial layer necessary for the molding lithography process. The glass substrate was flipped and aligned with the PVA-coated silicon wafer, and the previously prepared hydrogel precursor was injected into the chamber. Under a 10 mT magnetic field for 4 min, IONPs were aligned, followed by UV exposure (wavelength: 365 nm; intensity: 3 mW cm⁻²) for 2 min to complete the hydrogel polymerization, while maintaining the magnetic field during exposure. The stacked structure was immersed in water to dissolve the PVA sacrificial layer, releasing the silicon wafer and leaving the microrobot chassis on the glass wafer. The prepared microrobot chassis were ready for subsequent annealing of the ZnO nanorod seed layer.

Preparation of the ZnO Seed Solution: 5 mmol of zinc acetate dihydrate was dissolved in 0.654 mol of IPA at 85 °C (water bath) while stirring at 300 rpm for 15 min. During this process, the solution gradually turned white and turbid. Next, 5 mmol of triethylamine was added dropwise to the mixture, keeping the water bath temperature at 85 °C and stirring at 300 rpm for an additional 10 min. The solution then became clear and gradually turned translucent. After that, the mixture cooled to room temperature and was aged for at least 3 h to complete the preparation of the ZnO seed solution.

Figure 5. ROS generation and piezoelectric simulation of in situ-grown ZnO nanorods under acoustic stimulation. a) Schematic of the DMPO spin-trapping mechanism for superoxide ($O_2^{\bullet-}$) and hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet OH$), forming stable adducts DMPO-OOH and DMPO-OH, respectively. b) EPR spectra of DMPO-OOH showing six characteristic peaks of superoxide radicals, with signal intensity increasing from 0 to 10 min. c) EPR spectra of DMPO-OH displaying a typical four-peak pattern. d) COMSOL simulations of the electric potential distribution in spatially grown ZnO nanorods under different pressures (10, 50, and 100 MPa) and loading directions (left, right, and top).

ZnO Seed Annealing Process: After removing the silicon wafer, the microrobots bearing wafer were immediately transferred into the prepared ZnO seed solution for 10 min. Following immersion, the wafer was taken out and placed into an oven at 90 °C for a 5-min annealing process. These two steps constituted one treatment cycle. To ensure successful annealing of the ZnO seed layer onto the hydrogel surface, the treatment was repeated for three cycles. The seed-annealed wafer was then ready for the subsequent ZnO nanorod growth.

Preparation of ZnO Growth Solution: 15 mmol of zinc nitrate hexahydrate and HMTA were dissolved in 800 mL of DI water at room temperature and stirred for 30 min to ensure complete dissolution.

ZnO Nanorods Growing Process: The seed annealed sample was mounted onto an acrylic stand and immersed in an 800-mL beaker of ZnO growth solution. The wafer was positioned nearly vertically, with the microrobot side slightly tilted downward. The entire beaker was then placed in an oven and kept at 90 °C for 4 h to promote ZnO nanorod growth. After this period, the growth process was complete.

Release and Collection of ZnO Nanorods Incorporated Microrobots: After successfully growing ZnO nanorods on the microrobots, the glass wafer microrobot side was gently rinsed with a slow flow of PGMEA solvent to remove any residual ZnO particles that had settled from the growth solution on the surface. The wafer was then transferred into a fresh bath of 1-methoxy-2-propanol acetate solvent to dissolve the underlying PMMA sacrificial layer. As the PMMA layer dissolved, the microrobots gradually detached from the wafer and were collected into a bottle for subsequent testing.

Material Characterization: The surface morphology of ZnO nanorods grown on the hydrogel side of the microrobots was analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Hitachi Inc. SU8200 series, 2.0 kV). Elemental analysis of the individual nanorod was conducted through energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS, FEI Talos 200S). X-ray diffraction (XRD) spectrum measurements (Empyrean X-ray diffractometer, Bruker AXS D8 Advance, Cu K α) were performed on the ZnO-coated microrobot side over a 2θ range of 10° to 80°. Additionally, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM), and selected area diffraction (SAED) analyses were conducted separately on the individual ZnO nanorod sample.

Characterization of Shape Reconfiguration Capability: The microrobots were placed in a Petri dish filled with water and evaluated by alternating the temperature between 20 °C and 40 °C. Shape-morphing performance was recorded using optical imaging with commercial CCD cameras (BASLER Inc., a2A3840-45ucPRO and acA1920-150uc, Germany).

Evaluation of Microrobot Actuation Under External Rotating Magnetic Fields: The microrobots were placed into a water-filled chamber located at the center of three pairs of Helmholtz coils. An interface system was employed to control the strength of the magnetic field, the rotational frequency, and the direction of the magnetic field during actuation experiments.

Biocompatibility Test with MTT Assays: To evaluate the feasibility of microrobots for biomedical applications, their biocompatibility was assessed using MTT assays (Figure S6, Supporting Information). Human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) were incubated with microrobots for 72 h, during which ultrasonication was performed for 8 min once each day. After the treatment period, the microrobots maintained over 80% cell viability, indicating an acceptable level of biocompatibility.

Methods for In Vitro Antibacterial Testing of Microrobots: *E. coli* DSM 1103 (ATCC25922) was used for the antimicrobial test. A single colony from an LB agar plate was picked and inoculated into 2 mL of LB medium, followed by shaking at 37 °C and 200 rpm for 16 h. 5 μ L of the overnight culture was transferred into 5 mL of fresh LB medium and shaken at 37 °C and 220 rpm for 3 h until reaching log-phase. The bacteria were then washed three times with PBS buffer by centrifugation at 8000 \times g for 5 min and finally resuspended in 5 mL of PBS buffer. The optical density (OD₆₀₀) measurement was performed, and the bacteria were diluted to 10⁵ mL⁻¹ with PBS buffer. Before the antibacterial test, the robots stored in PGMEA solvent were taken with tweezers and thoroughly washed three times with PBS. Then, 0.5 mL of the bacterial suspension was mixed with 10 robots in a 15 mL Falcon tube, followed by ultrasonication on a plate.

After ultrasonication treatment, the bacteria were diluted 100 times with PBS buffer. 150 μ L of the diluted suspension was plated on an agar plate (\varnothing 90 mm), followed by incubation at 37 °C overnight. Each condition was plated and counted in triplicate.

Statistical Methods: All analyses were performed in GraphPad Prism (version 10.4.0, GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA). Data are presented as mean \pm SD unless stated otherwise. For each experiment, *n* denotes biological replicates (independent samples); technical replicates, when present, were averaged to yield one value per biological replicate.

Characterization of ROS Generation Under Ultrasonication: ROS generation under ultrasonication was characterized using EPR spectroscopy (Bruker A300 EMX Plus). DMPO served as a radical-trapping agent to capture transient free radicals. Samples (1 g L⁻¹) for EPR characterization were collected at 0, 5, and 10 min during ultrasonication and mixed with a 0.1 M DMPO solution. The mixture was subsequently transferred into capillary tubes for EPR measurements to detect and quantify free radical species.

Simulation of ROS Generation: The piezoelectric response of spatially in situ grown ZnO nanorods on the microrobot chassis to hydraulic pressure fluctuations was simulated using the finite element method (FEM) with COMSOL Multiphysics. Various pressure and loading conditions were considered to discuss the effects of these parameters. See more details in the supporting information.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Q.G. and J.W. conceived the research concept. Q.G., J.W., S.S., B.J.N., and S.P. participated in the discussion of the study. Q.G., F.L., and J.W. designed the experiments and developed the methodology. Q.G., J.G., Y.S., and J.W. optimized the fabrication process. Q.G. and J.G. carried out microrobot fabrication and functional materials synthesis. Q.G., J.G., and J.W. performed the characterization experiments and investigations. N.Q. and J.W. conducted the simulations. Q.G. and F.L. carried out the antibacterial experiments. H.Y. conducted the biocompatibility experiments. Q.G., F.L., E.Z., and J.W. wrote the original draft and prepared the figures and videos. Q.G., F.L., J.W., J.G., E.Z., J.P., G.C., S.S., B.J.N., and S.P. revised the manuscript. All authors interpreted the results and reviewed the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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